

Preliminary performance of the Ingot WFS with a Deformable Lens

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the characterization and experimental integration of a Deformable Lens (DL) within the Ingot Wavefront Sensor (I-WFS) test-bench. As a transmissive wavefront corrector, the DL offers a compact alternative to traditional deformable mirrors, enabling the introduction and correction of aberrations without complex optical redesign. Using a 4D interferometer, we define the dynamic range, linearity, and stability of the DL for low-order Zernike modes. We identify procedures required to mitigate hysteresis and ensure repeatable performance in open-loop configurations. Experimental results from the I-WFS bench demonstrate a high degree of correlation between laboratory signal maps and ray-tracing simulations. Furthermore, we implement a modal reconstruction algorithm using an interaction matrix approach, successfully recovering input wavefront shapes with a maximum residual error of 0.4λ . These results validate the DL as a viable tool for both generating controlled distortions and performing wavefront corrections, in the presence of low-order aberrations. This work establishes the calibration framework necessary for future closed-loop adaptive optics operations using the I-WFS.

Keywords: Ingot WFS, Wavefront Sensor, LGS, Deformable Lens, MAL, Zernike Modes, Adaptive Optics

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1. INTRODUCTION

Adaptive Optics (AO) has become an essential technology for ground-based telescopes, using Laser Guide Stars (LGSs) to provide high-resolution imaging across the sky. While sodium LGS systems—which excite the mesospheric sodium layer at altitudes above 85 km—offer higher sky coverage, they present significant challenges for the next generation of Extremely Large Telescopes (ELTs) [8, 2]. As telescope apertures increase, the 3D structure of the sodium layer causes the LGS to appear as an elongated beacon rather than a point source. This elongation degrades the performance of conventional sensors like the Shack-Hartmann and Pyramid WFS, leading to measurement errors and complex calibration requirements.

To overcome limitations of traditional sensors, the Ingot Wavefront Sensor (I-WFS) has been proposed as a new class of pupil-plane sensors specifically designed to match the 3D geometry of the LGS [19, 18, 17]. For the purpose of this work, we will talk about only the three pupil I-WFS configuration [20]. Unlike traditional sensors, the I-WFS is made of a prismatic reflecting device aligned with the focal plane of the elongated beacon. By splitting the LGS image into three distinct regions, see Figure 1, the sensor produces three pupils (I_A , I_B , and I_C) on the detector. The wavefront derivatives are then extrapolated by calculating the normalized difference in intensity between these pupils, pixel-wise, defined by the signals S_x and S_y ([16]):

$$S_x = \left(\frac{I_B - I_C}{I_A + I_B + I_C} \right) - \left(\frac{I_B - I_C}{I_A + I_B + I_C} \right)_{ref} \quad (1)$$

$$S_y = \left(\frac{I_A}{I_A + I_B + I_C} \right) - \left(\frac{I_A}{I_A + I_B + I_C} \right)_{ref} \quad (2)$$

In this configuration, pupils B and C provide information regarding the x -derivative (transverse to the elongation), while pupil A is dedicated to the y -derivative (longitudinal). By subtracting a non-aberrated reference measurement, the sensor isolates the atmospheric perturbations from the static geometry of the sodium beacon.

Recent development of the I-WFS has progressed from E2E simulations [12, 13, 23, 22] to successful laboratory demonstrations [4, 1]. Key milestones include the creation of automated alignment procedures [16, 5] to handle dynamic changes in the sodium layer profile [6, 7] and the integration of Deformable Lens (DL) technology for aberration study. Latest updates of the project are described in [11, 10, 14]. This paper details the experimental performance of the I-WFS, under the presence of a DL as a wavefront aberrator and is organised as follows: Section 2 describes the characterisation of this DL with an interferometer, including the calibration - Section 2.2

Figure 1. Working principle of the three pupil I-WFS. The two reflecting surfaces of the Ingot prism can be seen to produce two reflected beams, while the orange beam passes unperturbed by the prism and produces the transmitted beam. These beams respectively are re-imaged into three pupils: reflected pupils B,C and transmitted pupil A.

and linearity study of the DL - Section 2.1; Section 3 analyses the behavior of this DL when implemented on the I-WFS bench, first by comparing the signals with simulations - Section 2.1 and by building an Interaction Matrix I_m to perform wavefront reconstruction in Section 3.2.

2. CHARACTERIZATION OF THE DEFORMABLE LENS

The Multi-Actuator Adaptive Lens (MAL, AOL1825 model from Dynamic Optics srl [3]) or, as we refer here as Deformable Lens (DL) - a parallel with the widely used term Deformable Mirror (DM) - is a transmission piezoelectric-type wavefront corrector capable of generating aberrations up to the 4th radial order of Zernike polynomials. It is composed of two thin Willow glass optical windows filled with transparent liquid, matching the refractive index of the glass. Each glass window is bonded on the outer perimeter to a piezoelectric ring where bimorph actuators are glued. The ring is divided into nine sectors on each side, one for each actuator, comprising a total of 18 actuators that can be actuated independently. By applying a driving voltage to each actuator, it is possible to bend the glass membrane locally. Linearly combining the actuators, we are able to generate complex aberrations. In the astronomical field, the DL has proven its potential both during on-sky observations for small telescopes [15] and in a laboratory experiment to compensate low-order Non-Common Path Aberrations [21], or to exploit the full capabilities of a pyramid wavefront sensor [9].

The DL used in this work has a clear aperture of 25.50 mm, suitable for the pupil size of the I-WFS test-bench. The transmissive nature, compactness and the clear aperture sizes of the DL make this device suitable for an easy installation on already existing laboratory setups without the need of complex re-design or insertion of folding mirrors. For this reason, we found the opportunity to install this DL on the I-WFS test-bench and use it to introduce wavefront aberrations but also as a possible wavefront corrector. The possibility to place the DL on the pupil plane allows for preliminary testing of the quasi-closed-loop scenario in a laboratory setup.

Initial tests on the DL took place in a dedicated test bench composed of a 4D PhaseCam 4030 Interferometer (4D-I) to verify the aberrations introduced by the DL, a flat reference mirror (M1) for the double-pass interferometric test, and a beam expander (BE) to enlarge the interferometer beam to fully illuminate the lens clear aperture. The setup is illustrated in Figure 2.

The calibration of the lens was done by Dynamic Optics on a setup with a Shack Hartmann WFS in closed-loop. The resulting flat configuration had a residual wavefront error (WFE) of 0.0163λ RMS at $\lambda = 632.8$ nm. This flat corresponded to an array of actuator voltages that already used 33.8% of the actuators dynamic range, which poses a limitation to normal operations. We should point out that, when operated in open-loop — as will be the case in our setup — the same flat measured with the 4D-I showed a transmitted WFE of 0.7515λ RMS ($\lambda = 632.8$ nm, excluding tilts). Aberrations introduced by the BE and M1 have been removed prior to this measurement. To mitigate this, all interferometric measurements present in this work are made relative to this open-loop flat. The calibration procedures described here using the interferometer aim to characterise the performance of the lens in terms of dynamic range, linearity, repeatability and stability when operated in an open-loop configuration (which may deviate from closed-loop performance).

Figure 2. Test bench used to characterise the DL, with a 4D Interferometer.

Mode	Dynamic Range (λ , RMS)		Stability (RMS WFE)		Repeatability (RMS WFE)	
	Measured l.c.	Tech report l.c.	nm	λ	nm	waves
Vertical Astigmatism	[-3.5, +3.5]	[-3.91, +3.91]	80.3	0.13	56.4	0.089
Oblique Astigmatism	[-3.5, +3.5]	[-3.94, +3.94]	103.4	0.16	23.2	0.037
Horizontal Coma	[-0.65, +0.25]	[-1.14, +1.14]	92.8	0.147	35.9	0.057
Vertical Coma	[-0.5, +0.4]	[-1.16, +1.16]	44.9	0.071	20.7	0.032
Spherical	[-0.28, +0.15]	[-0.33, +0.33]	80.6	0.127	80.4	0.127
Flat	NA	NA	20.7	0.033	15.3	0.024

Table 1. Results of the characterisation of the DL, for five modes, regarding the dynamic range (non-saturating), the stability and repeatability of its shape. The last row refers to the characterisation of the flat.

A first important study was the definition of the dynamic range (DR) of amplitudes that can be applied with each mode without passing 90% of saturation of the DL actuators. The RMS amplitude of the aberrations applied to the DL are expressed as lens coefficients (l.c.), units of λ . In Table 1, we present the values obtained for five modes: Vertical Astigmatism, Oblique Astigmatism, Horizontal Coma, Vertical Coma, and Spherical; and compare with the DR provided in the technical report of the DL calibration. With this first analysis we opted for limiting our study only up until the spherical, since at this stage we were observing already reduced DR and stability issues when applying higher modes.

The 4D-I performs a fit to the first 8 Zernike polynomials of the incoming wavefront. The RMS amplitude of the aberrations measured with the 4D-I are expressed as real coefficients (r.c.), in units of λ of the modes: TiltX, TiltY, Defocus, Vertical Astigmatism, Oblique Astigmatism, Horizontal Coma, Vertical Coma and Spherical.

We performed stability tests on the DL by applying a single amplitude of each mode and acquiring measurements with the 4D-I every 30 seconds over 1.5 hours. The change in wavefront shape between the first and last measurements - indicates the stability of the applied modes. TiltX, TiltY and Defocus are left out of this calculation as they are seen to mostly vary with ambient temperature. Results are reported in Table 1. The test showed that these modes remained stable within an RMS WFE of < 104 nm, over the course of the measurements.

Repeatability was evaluated by repeatedly applying a single amplitude of each mode to the DL and recording measurements with the 4D-I every 3 minutes over a 30-minute period, relaxing the actuators in between measurements. This relaxation is a function that applies to each actuator a rapidly oscillating voltage between max and min values, converging to the flat voltages and reducing accumulated hysteresis. Results are presented in Table 1, again in terms of the RMS WFE of the wavefront. Most modes showed repeatability within < 81 nm RMS WFE. An important note is that repeatability WFE are systematically smaller than stability WFE, in which no relaxation was done. This indicates the impact of hysteresis over time on the lens shape and shows the importance of relaxing the lens in between measurements when operating in open-loop. Since the lens will be used in shorter time intervals than these measurements, with relaxation intercalated during use, these WFE values can be used as upper limit error estimation.

The same analysis of repeatability and stability, with the same time-scale, was extended onto the flat configuration of the lens, and the results can be seen in Table 1. Given the above stated RMS shape of 0.7515λ in open-loop, we are experiencing random errors of the order of 4% which can be neglected when compared to other modes errors.

2.1 Linearity

Perhaps the most critical test regarding the operation of the lens for our purposes is the assessment of the linearity of the modes. Without a truth sensor in parallel with the lens, it is of vital relevance to infer whether the lens has a linear response, the corresponding linearity ranges for each mode, and how uncorrelated the modes are from each other. To do so, we applied aberrations within the full DR of amplitudes of each mode and measured the resulting shape with the 4D-I.

The results of this test are reported in Figure 3, where the vertical scale reports the r.c. measured by the 4D-I and the horizontal scale reports the l.c. applied to the lens. In each panel the mode under study is highlighted in cyan. The main feature to point out is that Comas are linear inside the entirety of their DR but the same is not true for the astigmatisms. There also seems to be a correlation between Comas and Tilts. Moreover, the linearity slope for the modes is not unity, which is something that will be considered when converting from l.c. to r.c. In this sense, the measurements of the interferometer act as our truth sensor and provide wavefront measurements which are relative to the lens flat. The newly-found linearity ranges and linearity slopes are summarised in Table 2.

Aberration	Linearity slope	Linearity range (l.c., λ)
Vertical Astigmatism	-1.396	[-1,+3]
Oblique Astigmatism	1.475	[-2.5,+3]
Horizontal Coma	1.672	[-0.5,0.4]
Vertical Coma	-1.736	[-0.65,0.25]
Spherical	-1.263	[-0.27,0.15]

Table 2. Definition of the linearity range for five modes and the linearity slope, which relates lens coefficients (l.c.) to 4D-I measured real coefficients (r.c.)

Given the reduced DR and linearity range of the spherical mode, and considering also the results obtained regarding its stability and repeatability, we opted for leaving this mode out of the next tests.

2.2 DL–4D Interferometer Calibration and Mode Reconstruction

Building a Modes to Commands ($M2C$) and/or Commands to Modes ($C2M$) matrix is a common step of characterisation of wavefront correctors in AO. The goal is to establish a linear mapping between mode amplitudes (in l.c.) and the voltage inputs applied to the corrector actuators (and vice-versa). In this work, the calibration is based on the four Zernike modes previously studied. For each lens mode, choosing an amplitude A in the middle of the linearity range, the positive amplitude and negative amplitude values of the voltages (V_+ and V_-) are recorded. We define the matrix ($M2C$) as:

- $M2C \in \mathbb{R}^{18 \times 4}$ be the matrix containing voltage vectors $(V_+ - V_-)/2A$, where each column corresponds to the actuator patterns used to generate each of the 4 Zernike modes.

This matrix enables the computation of the actuator voltage vector $v \in \mathbb{R}^{18}$, relative to the flat, needed to generate a target mode vector $z_{l.c.} \in \mathbb{R}^4$.

Conversely, to retrieve the modal composition in l.c. $z_{l.c.}$ of a given voltage configuration, we define the inverse matrix ($C2M$) as the Moore-Penrose pseudo-inverse of the $M2C$.

These operations enable two key capabilities: forward control, predicting voltage commands required to produce a desired wavefront amplitude (within the four modes studied) and inverse reconstruction, estimating the wavefront amplitude from a given set of DL actuator voltages. These operations are only valid inside the linearity range of the four modes. They will be necessary during the reconstruction algorithms described in further sections.

Additionally, it becomes of interest to also have a conversion between r.c. and l.c., mapping the applied lens shape to the measured 4D shape. To do so, using the previous mode amplitudes A , we record the measured amplitudes in r.c. (Z_+ and Z_-). We define the matrix $Calibration(C)$ as:

- $C \in \mathbb{R}^{8 \times 4}$ be the matrix of Zernike r.c. $(Z_+ - Z_-)/2A$, where each column corresponds to the 4D interferometer measurements for each of the four modes.

This matrix enables the computation of the shape of the wavefront $z_{r.c.} \in \mathbb{R}^8$ as measured by the 4D corresponding to a certain shape $z_{l.c.} \in \mathbb{R}^4$.

3. DL ON THE I-WFS BENCH

The laboratory testing of the I-WFS is currently taking place at the INAF-Osservatorio Astronomico di Padova facilities. The experimental setup (well described in [7]) features a test bench specifically designed to assess the performance of an optical layout mimicking the ELT system with an I-WFS. More precisely, the bench aims to simulate the LGS source [6], its variability and imaging onto the I-WFS in a 1:1 magnification optical layout, generating an image of three pupils on a dedicated camera with accurate sampling.

For this study, the OLED screen was configured as a uniform source simulating a LGS elongation of 4.3 arcseconds at the subaperture farthest from the ELT laser launcher. The ingot prism was aligned to this source using the automatic alignment procedure [5], with the DL in the pupil plane and set to its flat configuration. All subsequent pupil image measurements and signal computations are referenced to this configuration. The flat configuration thus defines the reference signal, and the ingot is not re-aligned after this step.

Data acquisition involved using the DL to apply the Zernike aberrations defined in Section 2.1, within the limits of the established linearity range. For each DL setting, 10 pupil images were averaged (after dark-frame subtraction), and the S_x and S_y signal maps were computed with Equations 1 and 2. These signal maps will be used to compare with signals obtained with ray-tracing simulations.

Figure 3. Measurements regarding the linearity of the DL when five of its modes are used: Oblique Astigmatism, Vertical Astigmatism, Vertical Coma, Horizontal Coma and Spherical. Highlighted in blue is the main mode under study, while the full measurements by the interferometer may include contributions of other modes, in grey.

3.1 Zemax Simulation Comparison

For verification of the experimental results with the current ingot prism, we simulated the setup with the ray-tracing optical design software *Zemax OpticStudio*. The simulation allowed us to check the design parameters and get familiar with the ingot signals. The source used in the simulations presented below is a rectangular source that matches the OLED screen source characteristics. The second step of the simulation is to introduce in the Zemax model Zernike aberrations to test the I-WFS response to distortions. They have been added at the pupil level using a Biconic Zernike lens that allows to define the surface shape of the lens using Zernike Standard polynomials.

For the same modes, we simulated the resulting image of the pupils, and we compared the signals with those obtained in our lab setup. When analyzing the pupils and respective signals, some fine-tuning, such as clocking the simulated signals to match the setup orientation, was required. In order to obtain a higher SNR, we used a detector with the same dimensions as our laboratory set-up but binned 6×6 . Therefore, for a direct comparison of signal data from laboratory and simulations, all laboratory images were binned to 6×6 .

The results of this comparison are presented in Figure 4, for each mode a positive and negative amplitude is shown. It can be seen that the signals have a very good correspondence overall, while some discrepancies appear in the bottom of the pupil. These are more evident in the signals corresponding to Oblique Astigmatism and likely are due to a malfunctioning actuator.

Figure 4. Comparison of slopes (reference subtracted) obtained in the laboratory set-up, with the DL, and in the Zemax simulation. For each S_x and S_y , the difference between simulation and lab are shown, in the same colour scale. Here shown are the modes Oblique Astigmatism - amplitude 2λ , Vertical Astigmatism - amplitude 2λ , Horizontal Coma - amplitude 0.4λ and Vertical Coma - amplitude 0.2λ , amplitudes are l.c. RMS.

3.2 Matrix-vector-multiplication Reconstruction Algorithm

We proceeded to perform the modal Interaction Matrix I_m with the four studied modes. We opt for applying positive (Push, A) and negative (Pull, $-A$) amplitudes of each mode alternatively, in the sequence $[A, A, A, A; -A, -A, -A, -A]$ intercalated with the relaxation of the DL actuators. To each individual signal maps we subtract the signals obtained with the flat lens, which we use for reference, according to Equations 1 and 2. Signals obtained at every push are averaged $S_+ = [S_x, S_y]_+$, and the same for signals obtained with every pull, $S_- = [S_x, S_y]_-$. The final signal information to be used for the I_m is $(S_+ - S_-)/2A$, resulting in a $N \times 4$ matrix, N the number of subapertures of the pupil (in this case, depending on the sampling of the camera pixels). A Control Matrix (C_m) is obtained with I_m^\dagger . It maps wavefront measurements to Zernike modes.

We used these matrices to reconstruct different known modes applied to the DL, given as an array of l.c. $z_{l.c.}$. We studied not only the amplitudes of the modes used during the calibration but also a few others along the DR of the DL, including combinations of more than one mode. These l.c. are mapped into a real wavefront shape r.c. (related through matrix C).

In this way, we can easily compare applied l.c. with reconstructed l.c. The following plots show exactly this analysis for different aberrations applied, one example given for a single mode - Figure 5, left-hand panel, another for a combination of modes - Figure 5, right-hand panel. These plots compare the applied shape z_{input} with the measured shape $z_{measured}$, highlighting the main mode applied with the DL.

One can then go further and study the performance of the reconstruction algorithm by measuring the difference between applied coefficients and measured coefficients. This exact study was done and the difference is shown

in the bottom panel of Figure 5 for all different single modes (squared data points) and combination of modes (circle data points).

Figure 5. Example of reconstruction algorithm applied to: (*top panel*) single mode (2λ of Oblique Astigmatism) and (*middle panel*) combination of modes (2λ of Oblique Astigmatism and -2λ of Vertical Astigmatism). Residual between input and measured shape is shown for all modes and combinations tested in (*bottom panel*).

The method is able to reconstruct the shapes of these modes, matching the tests previously performed, while showing maximum residuals of the order of -0.4λ . This mismatch has been understood to rise due to relatively small differences in positioning of the DL (rotation) in the two optical benches where it has been tested (ingot and interferometer bench). Here it has been minimised as far as possible.

In AO the goal is often to obtain the voltage array necessary to correct for a wavefront shape measured by the wavefront sensor. In other words, an operator that maps wavefront slopes $S = [S_x, S_y]$ to actuator commands v . To obtain such an operator, we need to use the above defined $C2M$ matrix. This would then allow for open-loop and closed-loop operations, which are currently undergoing and whose results will be presented on a future work.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This work characterized a DL for use with the I-WFS test-bench. As a transmissive element, the DL proved to be a versatile tool for wavefront modulation, allowing for the introduction of controlled aberrations without the complex optical redesign required by reflective DMs. Through interferometric characterization, we defined the linearity ranges for astigmatism and comas and identified the relaxation procedure as key to mitigate hysteresis and ensure shape repeatability in open-loop operation. Integration with the I-WFS bench demonstrated a sensitivity of the sensor signals to the "clocking" of the corrector. Using a matrix-vector-multiplication reconstruction algorithm, we successfully recovered input wavefront shapes with a maximum residual error of 0.6λ . Higher residuals are usually expected in such static open-loop operations, while in closed-loop they tend to be reduced. These results validate the DL as both an aberrator and a potential corrector for the I-WFS, for low-order aberrations mostly. This study establishes the calibration framework required for upcoming open-loop and closed-loop correction experiments, which will be the focus of future work.

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